

Customer Relations and Use of Online Shopping Sites

Bahar Urhan Torun, Havva Nur Tarakcı

Abstract—At the present time, online marketing has become the common target of small and full-scale organizations. Today's humanbeing who has to spend most of their time in front of the computer because of his job, prefers to socialize by internet due to the easy access to technology. So online marketing area expands day by day. All business organizations from the smallest to the biggest are in a race in order to get a cut from the virtual market share in an extreme competitive environment. However these organizations which use the internet to reach more consumers cannot determine their target group accurately, so this is the biggest handicap of online marketing sales nowadays. The aim of this study is to determine some significant elements about need for communicating efficiently with the consumer on the internet on online marketing. The strategies that can be used in order to increase sales and the limitations of virtual environment where cannot be communicated with the consumer face to face are argued in this study's scope. As a consequence it is thought that to study on this subject because of lacking and also being limited efficiency of researches and outputs. Within this scope suggesting some proposals about how to communicate efficiently with the consumer and also offering the consumers' demands efficiently is the essential objective of this study.

Keywords—Communication, competition, consumer, online marketing.

I. INTRODUCTION

THIS is an indisputable truth that today's people see the internet as an important part of their daily life. In the commercial world where is a huge competition war some truths about technology have been realized, and competitors have been using the internet for delivering their products to the consumer in recent years. The modern consumers spend most of their time on internet in their work or private life, and they realized the online shopping reality and noticed this activity makes their life easier.

Online shopping serves some advantages such as low price, easy and comfortable shopping opportunity, 7/24 shopping chance, wide product scale, etc. And traditional shopping has handicaps such as waiting in a queue, crowded stores, wasting of time for transportation, etc. When the consumer compare them, he/she can find online shopping more advantageous.

In spite of having very important advantages, online shopping is not developed in desired level. Because there are some disincentives keep the consumers away from this shopping channel. These disincentives are some concerns about security issues on giving credit card information, personal information; buying without seeing and trying the product; wanting to touch and see the real size of the product;

B. Urhan Torun and H. NurTarakcı are with the Selçuk University, Faculty of Communication and Department of Public Relations and Publicity, Konya, 42250, Turkey (e-mail: baharurhantorun@gmail.com, hnuryildirim@selcuk.edu.tr).

long delivery period, and slow communication speed during shopping period. These are affecting online shopping attitude negatively.

The online shopping sector has been growing in every passing day, and organizations need to make customers satisfied. They can easily measure the customers' satisfaction level in electronic environment. Digital generation prefers online shopping instead of traditional shopping and, they think it means saving time in the rush of life. And also an organization with weak customer relationship management has to loose the competition war against its rivals.

II. CUSTOMER RELATIONS MANAGEMENT

A. Customer Concept

Customer concept is used for organizations or people who pay for services or products of some operations. Customer is the reason of a foundation's existence [1]. Customer can be defined as a person who shops regularly from a store or a firm [2]. Customer is a base of an operation's existence and success. Customer is the real boss of all employees and supplies the operation's income, future and guarantee. That is why the customer deserves all interest, appreciation and thanking [3]. An organization cannot exist without their customers.

According to another definition, customer is a person who has bought or possibly will buy a product or service from a firm. Customer is a restricted source in a market so, firms have to reach more and more customers day by day in order to increase their share in market and try to sell more products or services to their current customers. In this point of view customer is a person that the firms have to interested in and keep in touch with him or her all the time. In this sense, communicate with the customers, going to the appointment and record the conversation are important to gather some information about the customer [4]. There are some types of customer:

Current customer: This type of customer always buys the firms' service or product. **Prospects:** This type of customer is not firm's customer yet. But the firm contacts with him or her to sell its products or services. **Old customer:** This type of customer is former customer of the firm but somehow their business between the customer and the firm has ended. **New customer:** This type of customer has bought the firm's service or product for the first time. **Target customer:** The firm aims to add this type of customer among its currents [5].

B. Customer Relations Management Concept

Customer relations is a process is established between customer and organization that based on satisfaction of mutual benefit and needs and, involves all actions before and after the

sale. That is a primitive and oldfashioned idea to think customer relations as “it only involves sales process”. In addition to that both sides have advantages by positive customer relations as a behavior pattern [6]. CRM (*Customer Relationship Management*) is a customer centric strategy and good practising it, and is related to organizations’ all units. CRM is a very important approach among modern sales approaches.

It is basically based on a close and direct relation between firm-customer and, producer-consumer. CRM is a strategy aimed to give price/quality balance continuously to the customers just as they expect. As a result of the added value gained from the customers, the organizations increase profit [7].

The concept of CRM can be defined in many ways [8].

- * CRM involves methodology and products that are used for directing customer relations.
- * CRM is a management concept that is used for retain the firms’ optimum customers without increasing their costs, increase customer relation’s value, in this way they can increase their profit.
- * CRM is a business strategy culture that is discovered to activate sale, marketing and service period.
- * CRM is to design as business and knowledge flow according to primarily customers’ needs, secondarily organization’s needs.
- * CRM is to understand the customers’ needs, to know them and to develop products and services according to their needs.

Gathering information about customers during all the interactions with them is the essence of CRM. Customer gives very important information as they communicate with the organization (by telephone, internet or face to face etc.). The organization has to design CRM process in order to gather these information and record them.

These information which are recorded in data warehouses have to be designed in order to be easily reached by the employees whenever they communicate with the customers. Thus, the customers do not have to give information about themselves each time they call the organization [9]. Beyond all these definitions, the organizations adopt CRM have some specific starting point [10].

- * Organizations want to sell more products to one customer instead of one product to more customers.
- * Organizations want to develop longterm and learner-based relation instead of one broken off. Because customers accept to pay %15-20 more price when they satisfied with the product or service they have bought before.

C. Benefits of CRM

CRM gives very important clues about how to use human sources and technology efficiently in order to better understanding the customer.

If CRM studies are made succesfully and effectively there are some benefits for the organizations. These benefits are [11] :

- * Being a firm which gives better customer services
- * Answering customer faster and truer
- * Increasing quantity of cross selling and advanced level of selling the products
- * Transforming sales offers to orders, making easier sales forces’ work
- * More beneficial working of call center
- * Being fast and understandable in marketing and sales process
- * Finding and creating new customers opportunity
- * Increasing profit and customer loyalty

The chief benefits of CRM understanding and application are presented below [12]:

- * Via application of CRM sales and marketing departments in the context of “process management” organizations can get rid of being random and reach “long-termed customer relations”.
- * In a world that the products are very similar (product parity), the only way to create variation and gain an advantage over their competitors is that to know the customer one to one, and *the direct marketing*.
- * The money is spent on CRM project can be got back in many ways: Gains may be huge considering that sum of additional sales to current customers; retaining the current customers; opportunities to increase customer share, and on the other side costs of saving from sales; marketing and marketing communication activities, and intercorporate communication activities.
- * With CRM, organizational activities are designed according to customers’ demands. So this approach makes easier gaining benefit for all departments of the organization.
- * CRM can wondrously combine sales, marketing and customer relations by the internet opportunities. Organizations can gather customer information when they work with them face to face, and thanks to variety of communication channels (email, telephone, internet, etc.). They can combine those information gathered from face to face communication with the new information data gathered from communication channels. CRM can easily do this activity. In other words, the information which are gained by both traditional sales channels and alternative channels can be synthesised. So it means that maximum customer information and communication opportunities.

D. CRM Strategy

In real terms, for being customer focused and applying CRM strategy, organizations have to adopt all the studies below in their all departments [13].

1. Customer Focused Mission:

Mission determines a firm’s existential philosophy and directs the firm’s all operations in background.

It is based on turning the customer into one of the mission’s critical elements. So there can be formed the thought of the customer’s priority in the organization’s all works.

2. Customer Focused Goals:

The decisions that were made in customer relations strategy spread to all departments of the organization. Each department creates its own working plan and defines how to achieve these goals. For example if the organization wants to increase keeping customers rate to %5, the departments have to define their own share of the strategies to fulfill the objective.

3. Customer Focused Strategy:

The employees in the firm have critical roles. If they do not support customer focused strategy, it is very difficult to satisfy the expectations of the customers. In this case there must be made some intercorporate marketing campaigns in order to gain the customers. Publishing a notice in order to tell the importance of the strategy, organizing meetings, providing training are some of the methods that for both pull the customers into the project and provide the customer with information.

Fig. 1 CRM process

The most easy and effective way rewarding the customer focused success is that to make the employees responsible and proactive on the studies to develop customer relations, and create reward systems to encourage them.

4. Innovator Customer Focused Services and Products:

Defining customers' demands proactively and trying to develop products and service in this way is the foundation of CRM. In order to provide that, the firm has to be close to its customers to understand their demands. It means continuous customer researches, regular customer satisfaction evaluation, and open feedback channels.

5. Defining Customers' Variable Demands:

The more a product is useful for the customers, the more the customer remains in the organization. Because there will be no

reason to leave. They are very important to be successful for an organization that to create product portfolio as communicating with the customers all the time and seeing how can change their wishes and demands in time.

6. Data Processing and Telecommunication Support:

CRM applications have to be supported and made easier by relevant technologies. It means that the information about the customers have to be ready whenever they are needed as updated, right and in time in every part of the firm. This technology has to answer the needs which will appear in the future.

7. Customer Focused Database:

CRM requires interactive databases where the customers' information are kept in order, significant and, useful format. These information are true personal info, relation duration, info about the product or service has bought, former interviews, gathered data about marketing communication, total value and profitability of the customer.

One of the very important common features of the successful firms is to make an effort to satisfy the customers. Organizations provide the customer's satisfaction by producing qualified service or product. So they gain their customers' loyalty and success that much. It can be displayed as in Fig. 2 [14]:

Fig. 2 Organization success chain

III. USE OF INTERNET AND ONLINE SHOPPING

Digitized information flow change considerably people's and organization's usages and wishes. Information technologies and systems vary people's and organization's activity borders with no bounds so this makes important changes people's and organization's roles. Especially with the development of the internet technologies chain of distribution and in terms of functional all algorithms' integration has become possible. Utilization of informatics and communication technologies has become the most important condition of being information society. Becoming widespread of using internet in various fields of economic life increases social life quality so consumers' behaviors, habits and shopping styles have extremely changed. By this way the internet's effects on society, culture and consumer are becoming more and more important from the point of academical environment and practitioners [15].

A. Online Shopping and Online Customers

Progress on internet technologies enable the organization to reach the customer all over the world easily. Customers benefit from online shopping especially in terms of saving time and easiness. In spite of the concerns about security online shopping has become popular over the last years. This tendency is based on especially increase number of people who can access internet in workplace or house thanks to modems and online service substitution [16]. Increase of the online customers' number is more than increase of the number of internet users so, it shows that more and more people prefers to shop online. This increase can be seen as the same about the volume of online shopping on internet [17].

It is reported in 2006 that about 627 million people has shopped all over the world [18]. Internet World Stats Research Company defined the number of internet users in 2010 as 825.1 million people in Asia, 475.1 million people in Europe and, 266.2 million people in America. ABI Research Company has declared the volume of shopping on the internet will reach 119 billion dollars by year 2015 [19]. According to AC Nielsen's 2007 report the most purchased products' rates are books %34, videos/DVDs/games %22, plane tickets/reservations %21 and, clothes/accesory/shoes %20 [20]. According to the 2010 report of Eurostats the most purchased products or services are travel/accomodation %51, clothes/sports equipment %46, home needs %37 [21].

B. Preventing and Affecting Factors Online Shopping

Ernst and Young (2000) has reported about preventing and affecting factors online shopping the users prefers to shop online because of such reasons as competitive prices, easiness of using, variety of product range [22]. But these users have some concerns about some issues such as shipping charges, buying without seeing, giving credit card details, privacy of personal information etc.

The success of the electronic commerce is partially measured by customers' trust in sellers and products they cannot see face to face. Without trust to think about building and maintaining trade relation is very difficult. As the internet is a new distribution channel with high potential, it is very important need to discover the factors affects the customer's trust.

IV. SELCUK UNIVERSITY COMMUNICATION FACULTY STUDENTS ORIENTED CUSTOMER RELATIONS AND ONLINE SHOPPING ANALYSIS

A. The Aim of the Research:

The aim of the research is to determine the Selcuk University communication Faculty's students' online shopping use and satisfaction and, accordingly present some evaluation results.

B. The Importance of the Research:

By this research Selcuk University Communication Faculty's students' demographical attributes are primarily presented in general. Then, the students' online shopping level and habits of use are tried to be determined by

questions related their internet knowledge and online shopping use habits.

C. Hypothesis of the Research:

Selcuk University Communication Faculty's students' internet use habits oriented thesis in the survey are sufficient for presenting the students' online shopping use habits. Chosen research method is appropriate to the aim and subject of the research and solutions of the problems. Survey participants is sufficient enough to determine Selcuk University Communication Faculty's students' online shopping use habits and satisfaction.

D. Limitations of the Research:

Research findings reflects the faculty's students' perception about their online shopping use and satisfaction level on the date which survey has been done. Reliability and validity of the data which has been gathered by the survey is restricted to the technique is used for collecting data. The research data has been collected by only using survey technique not interview, observation techniques etc. so, this is another restraint of the research.

E. Research Technique:

There are some explanations about the research technique, the study's population and sample, developing and application the data collecting tool and instructions about data analysis in this part.

1. Research Method:

In this study about Selcuk University Communication Faculty's students' social media using habits during the voting period, descriptive survey model is based on. By the questionnaire is applied to the students the data has been collected and in the evaluation process frequency analysis, T test, chi square and correlation, likert scale with standard deviation and mean are used.

2. Population and Sample of the Study:

In the research Selcuk University students have been chosen as universe, communication Faculty students have been chosen as sample. When the sample was chosen random sample method was applied and, it has been limited with 190 people (13 questionnaire were invalid).

3. Developing the Data Collecting Tool:

When the data is needed for the research has been collected, questionnaire method is used. In the first part of the research the students' use of internet information has been tried to reach. In the second part the students' online shopping habits have been tried to determine. In the third part mostly the students' online shopping habits have been detailed and their customer relations satisfaction and which products or services are bought by students has been tried to defined.

4. Applying the Data Collecting Tool:

In the questionnaire form the first your age, your gender questions have been asked as open ended. In addition to these thereby developing some attitude questions by likert scale

subscription levels have been determined which affect the factors on online shopping behavior and customer relations satisfaction. The collected data was analyzed by using SPSS 15.0 package software in electronic environment. From the students' answers by using frequency analysis some prospects about current situation of the internet use have been tried to be presented. The next stage is to determine online shopping use related to customer relations. Accordingly online shopping and customer relations satisfaction relation has been researched and by doing T-test, chi square and correlation analysis online shopping behavior and use habits have been correlated. In attitude questions are prepared by likert scale descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) have been calculated.

V. RESEARCH AND FINDINGS

A. Demographic Specification of Respondents

TABLE I
DISTRIBUTION OF RESPONDENTS BY AGE

Age	Number	Percent	Valid Percent
18	5	2,8	3,0
19	15	8,5	9,1
20	20	11,3	12,1
21	36	20,3	21,8
22	38	21,5	23,0
23	23	13,0	13,9
24	19	10,7	11,5
25	5	2,8	3,0
26	1	,6	,6
27	1	,6	,6
28	2	1,1	1,2
Total	165	93,2	100,0

When it is looked at distributions of subjects who have responded the survey, it is seen that the ones who are 22 years old have the highest rate by %23,0. The ones who are 21 years old follow this order by %21,8 and who are 23 follow by %13,9. Respondents at the age of 26 and 27 have the lowest rate by % 6.

TABLE II
DISTRIBUTION OF RESPONDENTS BY GENDER

	Number	Percent	Valid Percent
Female	86	48,6	48,9
Male	90	50,8	51,1
Total	176	99,4	100,0

When it is taken a look at distributions of survey respondents by gender, %46,6 of them are consisted of female respondents; then, %50,8 are consisted of the male. In this respect, it is observed that respondents display an equable distribution in terms of the distribution of respondents by gender.

Once the departments at which survey respondents study are analysed, it is seen that %36,2 are Public Relations and Publicity, %28,2 are Radio-Television and Cinema and %35,6 are Journalism students. Most of the respondents are consisted of students at the Department of Public Relations and

Publicity. We can say again that there is an equable distribution among the departments of respondents in here.

TABLE III
DISTRIBUTION OF RESPONDENTS BY DEPARTMENTS

	Number	Percent	Valid Percent
Public Relations and Publicity	59	33,3	36,2
Journalism	58	32,8	35,6
Radio-Television and Cinema	46	26,0	28,2
Total	163	92,1	100,0

When distributions of subjects who have responded the survey are taken into consideration, it is regarded on one hand %2,3 are at prep class; on the other hand, %13,1 are at 4th, %21,7 are at 2nd, %30,9 are at 3rd and %32,0 are at 1st class. While the most of the subjects are at 1st class, the least of them are at prep class.

TABLE IV
DISTRIBUTION OF RESPONDENTS BY CLASSES

	Number	Percent	Valid Percent
Prep Class	4	2,3	2,3
1st Class	56	31,6	32,0
2nd Class	38	21,5	21,7
3rd Class	54	30,5	30,9
4th Class	23	13,0	13,1
Total	175	98,9	100,0

TABLE V
DISTRIBUTION OF RESPONDENTS BY THEIR MONTHLY EXPENSE

	Number	Percent	Valid Percent
250 and below	14	7,9	8,0
251-500	77	43,5	44,3
501-1000	70	39,5	40,2
1001 and more	13	7,3	7,5
Total	174	98,3	100,0

When it is looked at the distribution of subjects who have responded the survey by their monthly expense, it is seen that % 44,3 spend 21-500 TL, %40,2 spend 501-1000 TL, %8,0 spend 250 TL and below and %7,5 spend 1001 TL and over per month.

TABLE VI
THE DISTRIBUTION OF RESPONDENTS BY THEIR ACCOMODATION STATE

	Number	Percent	Valid Percent
Village, Town	50	28,2	28,4
County	43	24,3	24,4
City	70	39,5	39,8
Metropolis	13	7,3	7,4
Total	176	99,4	100,0

When it is asked to the subjects about their accomodation state, %39,8 have responded it as 'city', %28,4 have given the respond 'village, town' and %7,4 have responded 'metropolis'.

Once the distribution of respondents is taken into consideration by their settlements in which they have lived for the longest time, it is seen that %46,3 have lived in metropolis,

%22,9 have lived in city, %18,9 have lived in county and %12,0 have lived in village/town.

TABLE VII
DISTRIBUTION OF RESPONDENTS BY THEIR LONGEST-LIFE SETTLEMENT

	Sayı	Yüzde	Geçerli Yüzde
Village, Town	21	11,9	12,0
County	33	18,6	18,9
City	40	22,6	22,9
Metropolis	81	45,8	46,3
Total	175	98,9	100,0

B. The Computer and Internet Usage Level of Respondents

TABLE VIII
FINDINGS RELATED TO RESPONDENTS' OWNING A PERSONAL COMPUTER

	Number	Percent	Valid Percent
Yes	156	88,1	90,2
No	17	9,6	9,8
Total	173	97,7	100,0

When the subjects were asked whether they own a personal computer, it is regarded that %90,2 have given the respond 'yes' and %9,8 have responded as 'no'. It could be clearly suggested that most of the respondents own a personal computer.

TABLE IX
FINDINGS RELATED TO RESPONDENTS' HAVING INTERNET CONNECTIVITY IN THEIR SETTLEMENT

	Number	Percent	Valid Percent
Yes	161	91,0	94,2
No	10	5,6	5,8
Total	171	96,6	100,0

When it is considered whether respondents have an internet connectivity in the place where they live, it is seen that %94,2 have internet connectivity, %5,8 do not have any internet connectivity.

TABLE X
DISTRIBUTION OF RESPONDENTS BY THE PLACE OF CONNECTING TO INTERNET

	Number	Percent	Valid Percent
The Place Where I Live	147	83,1	85,5
Internet Cafe	5	2,8	2,9
School	8	4,5	4,7
Other	12	6,8	7,0
Total	172	97,2	100,0

Once it is looked at the place where respondents connect to internet, it is seen that %85,5 in the place where they live, %4,7 at school, %2,9 in an internet café, %7,0 in other places connect to internet. It is observed that most of the respondents connect to internet in the place where they live.

When it is looked at respondents' primary internet using aims, it is followed that %52,0 with the aim of intercommunication and/or texting, %23,1 with the aim of research and/or informing, %13,9 with the aim of entertainment, %7,5 with the aim of film, songs etc. download and %3,5 with other aims use the internet. On looking at the

distribution of respondents' daily internet using duration, it is seemed that %41,9 use the internet for 3-4 hours, %34,4 use the internet for 1-2 hours, %21,5 use the internet 5-6 hours, %12,2 use the internet 7 hours and over a day. Most of the respondents spend time on the internet for 3-4 hours a day. When it is asked to respondents whether they shop on the internet or not, %56,7 give the respond 'yes' and %43,3 respond it as 'no'. From this point of view, it is possible to say that most of the respondents shop online.

TABLE XI
DISTRIBUTION OF RESPONDENTS BY THEIR PRIMARY AIMS OF USING THE INTERNET

	Number	Percent	Valid Percent
Intercommunication, Texting	90	50,8	52,0
Entertainment	24	13,6	13,9
Research, Informing	40	22,6	23,1
Film, Songs Etc. Download	13	7,3	7,5
Other	6	3,4	3,5
Total	173	97,7	100,0

TABLE XII
THE DISTRIBUTION OF RESPONDENTS BY THEIR DAILY INTERNET USING DURATION

	Number	Percent	Valid Percent
1-2 hours	42	23,7	24,4
3-4 hours	72	40,7	41,9
5-6 hours	37	20,9	21,5
7 hours and more	21	11,9	12,2
Total	172	97,2	100,0

TABLE XIII
FINDINGS ABOUT RESPONDENTS' ONLINE SHOPPING

	Number	Percent	Valid Percent
Yes	97	54,8	56,7
No	74	41,8	43,3
Total	171	96,6	100,0

TABLE XIV
RESPONDENTS' LEVEL OF MONTHLY ONLINE SHOPPING

	Number	Percent	Valid Percent
never	44	24,9	33,1
1-3 times	73	41,2	54,9
4-6 times	12	6,8	9,0
7 times and more	4	2,3	3,0
Total	133	75,1	100,0

Once respondents' level of monthly online shopping is regarded, it is seen that %54,9 do it 1-3 times, %9,0 shop 4-6 times, %3,0 shop 7 times or more on the internet. %33,1 of the respondents never shop online.

When respondents are asked about products which they buy most online, %40,3 respond as 'textile/clothing', %19,4 give the answer 'technological/electronic products', %12,0 say 'book', %10,5 give the answer 'accessory/souvenir', %4,2 respond as 'cosmetics' and %13 reply as 'other'.

When it is asked to respondents 'Would you suggest your neighbourhood online shopping?', %52,0 have responded 'yes', %42,9 have responded 'no'.

TABLE XV
DISTRIBUTION OF RESPONDENTS BY THE PRODUCT THEY BUY MOST ONLINE

	Responds		Percent of Respondents
	Number	Percent	
Technological-Electronic Products	37	19,4%	35,2%
Textile-Clothing	77	40,3%	73,3%
Accessory-Souvenir	20	10,5%	19,0%
Cosmetics	8	4,2%	7,6%
Book	23	12,0%	21,9%
Other	26	13,6%	24,8%
Total	191	100,0%	181,9%

TABLE XVI
FINDINGS ON WHETHER RESPONDENTS SUGGEST THEIR NEIGHBOURHOOD ONLINE SHOPPING

	Number	Percent	Valid Percent
Yes	92	52,0	57,1
No	69	39,0	42,9
Total	161	91,0	100,0

C.Reviews of Respondents about Online Shopping

When reviews of people who have responded the survey about online shopping are examined, I can shop in safe (Mean. = 2,81), I can get service after sale (MEAN. = 2,78), I can shop enjoyably (MEAN. = 2,65) clauses emerge as the most important values on shopping online. I have a range of product selections and There is no problem of car park, transportation (MEAN. = 1,91), There is no problem of waiting for the queue (MEAN. = 1,88) clauses are seen as the least important.

TABLE XVII
REONDENTS' DEDUCTIONS ON ONLINE SHOPPING

	N.	Min.	Max.	Mean	SD
I can learn suggestions	171	1	5	2,12	,92
I have a range of product selections	171	1	5	1,91	,87
I shop for 7/24	171	1	5	2,32	1,25
I can learn expert reviews about products	171	1	5	2,51	1,05
I get acknowledged about products in detail	171	1	5	2,14	,97
I ensure saving of time	172	1	5	2,15	1,08
There is no problem of waiting for the queue	171	1	5	1,88	1,00
There is no problem of car park, transportation	172	1	5	1,91	,99
It provides shopping ease	172	1	5	1,95	1,03
I get the opportunity to buy cheap product	171	1	5	2,10	1,06
I get ease of payment	172	1	5	2,31	1,13
I can shop enjoyably	172	1	5	2,65	1,17
I can shop in safe	172	1	5	2,81	1,20
I can get service after sale	170	1	5	2,78	1,16
I get the opportunity to compare products or prices	171	1	5	1,99	1,05

D.Evaluation of the Problems which Respondents Confront at Online Shopping

Once values of the problems which people who have responded the survey confront at online shopping are examined, Being sent of the used product (MEAN. =3,52), Not being packaged of the product (MEAN. = 3,30), Being sent of a different product (equivalent) instead of the ordered product (MEAN. = 3,14), Troubles on the process of taking order (MEAN. = 3,12) clauses emerge as the most important problems which are met at online shopping.

Sending a message about the product which was seemed to be in stock is not any more after order (MEAN = 2,62), Late delivery of ordered products (MEAN. = 2,61), Giving late replies to customer complaints (MEAN. = 2,56) clauses are considered as the problems which have the least value.

VI.CONCLUSION

In this research, habits of the respondents on using the computer and internet, their values on shopping online and problems which they confront at online shopping have been analysed. In this direction, it has been seen that respondents have a personal computer and internet connectivity in the place where they live. When it is looked at the aim of the respondents' using the internet, it is seen that the most is communication and/or texting by %52,0. Then, daily internet using duration has been detected as 3-4 hours by %41,9.

TABLE XIII
RESULTS ABOUT PROBLEMS WHICH RESPONDENTS CONFRONT AT ONLINE SHOPPING

	Number	Min.	Max.	MEAN	SD
Being sent of the false product	174	1	5	2,75	1,17
Being sent of broken product	174	1	5	2,69	1,15
Being sent of lacking product	172	1	5	2,91	1,10
Not being packaged of the product	173	1	5	3,30	1,06
Being deformed of the product package	173	1	5	3,00	1,08
Being dirty of the product package	172	1	5	2,96	1,11
Obstructing product return	173	1	5	2,68	1,24
Being damaged of sent products during transportation	173	1	5	2,84	1,15
Late delivery of ordered products	172	1	5	2,61	1,17
Giving late replies to customer complaints	172	1	5	2,56	1,17
Not being removed of customer complaints	174	1	5	2,70	1,12
Sending a message about the product which was seemed to be in stock is not any more after order	174	1	5	2,62	1,21
Being sent of the used product	171	1	5	3,52	1,07
Not being able to reach units to communicate on removing product breakdowns	174	1	5	3,00	1,15
Troubles on the process of taking order	172	1	5	3,12	1,02
Being sent of a different product (equivalent) instead of the ordered product	168	1	5	3,14	1,10
Being sent in lack of product usage tools (accessories)	172	1	5	2,97	1,14
Not being of opportunities of monitoring the ordered products (transporter/product tracking)	172	1	5	2,99	1,16
Delaying the return of the returned product's fee	172	1	5	2,76	1,09
Making mistakes on the definition of the products in stock	173	1	5	2,78	1,07
Not being of communication depending on interactivity (mutual)	174	1	5	2,81	1,09
Not existing of customer service hotline to be informed about the product	173	1	5	2,95	1,15
Being sent of another product instead of the product sent in service	172	1	5	3,05	1,11
Inadquacy in factors to usage ease of the product (label, package, user guide)	172	1	5	3,04	1,11

Once it is taken a look at findings on whether respondents shop on the internet or not, it is regarded that there is not too

much difference. While %56,7 of the subjects shop online, %43,3 do not use the internet for shopping.

The levels of the respondents' shopping online has been so: 1-3 times the most by %54,9 and 7 times and more the least by %3,0. Whereas the product which respondents buy most online is textile products by %40,3, technological/electronic products follow it by %19,4. %52,0 of the respondents suggest their neighbourhood shopping online. In the first range of reviews of respondents' shopping online have I can shop in safe (MEAN. = 2,81), I can get service after sale (MEAN. = 2,78), I can shop enjoyably (MEAN. = 2,65) clauses come. I get a range of product selection and There is no car park problem (A.= = 1,91), There is no problem of waiting for the queue (MEAN. = 1,88) clauses are seen as the least important.

When evaluations about problems which ones who have responded the survey confront at online shopping have been analysed, Being sent of used product (MEAN. = 3,52), Not being packaged of the product (MEAN. = 3,30), Being sent of a different product (equivalent) instead of the ordered product (MEAN. = 3,14), Troubles on the process of taking order (MEAN. = 3,12) clauses appear as the most important problems which are met at online shopping. Sending a message about the product which was seemed to be in stock is not any more after order (MEAN. = 2,62), Late delivery of ordered products (MEAN. = 2,61), Giving late replies to customer complaints (MEAN. = 2,56) clauses are seen as the problems which have the least value.

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